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FIBER REINFORCED COMPOSITE ANGLES
ANALYSIS AND DESIGN RULES

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ABSTRACT

The generalized use of composite material in primary structures gives new critical attention points in the structural design. One of them is the case of angle laminates. This configuration is extensively used in structural items such as angles, cleats, club-foot fittings, spar and rib feet, etc.. Load conditions, which are not critical for the structural integrity in metallic materials, can produce a level of interlaminar stresses in the composite angles, high enough to cause severe delamination and therefore the failure of the structure. A way to ensure the strength of this kind of structure is needed.

C.A.S.A. has produced analysis methods and design rules for composite angles based on the experience reached in the AIRBUS and EFA programs, and supported by testing activities. Analysis methods are development of theoretical stress calculation (i.e. interlaminar radial and shear stresses) using stress functions or directly solving the differential equations of equilibrium with several aproximative assumptions. Testing activities have three main objectives. First, to identify the load distribution and failure criteria. Second, to determine the interlaminar stress allowables that depend on material and manufacturing process. And finally to validate the theoretical analysis.

Based on these analytical and test results it is possible to define some design rules to minimize the delamination problem in the angle corner.

KEYWORDS: Failure, interlaminar; Joint, bolted; Delamination; Three-dimensional; Design methodology.

1. INTRODUCTION

The composite materials play an important role in the design of aeronautical structures. One of the structural elements which have been conventionally designed in metal are all kind of angles, due to difficulties in manufacturing and in analysis. For instance: Bolted Angles, Cleats, C spars, rib shear ties and skin splices jointed in tension. The design of these parts in carbon fiber composite would allow a better integrated design, would reduce weight, would minimize the number of pieces, and would avoid corrosion and electromagnetic incompatibilities.

Taking this in mind, CASA has developed a methodology of analysis which permit to design and to analyze angles built in composites. This procedure has been validated with test results. The testing activities have three main objectives. First, to identify the load distribution and failure criteria. Second, to determine the interlaminar stress allowables that depends on material and manufacturing process. And finally to support the theoretical analysis.

The analytical procedures to calculate the stresses are summarized in this report. These methods are based in the differential equations of equilibrium with several approximate assumptions (Simple Procedure), or based on the stress functions proposed in Reference (1) for orthotropic curved beams (Complex Procedure).

The failure criteria used is the one proposed in Reference (2), where there is a quadratic interaction between the radial and interlaminar stresses. This criterion is represented in the figure 1.

Both methods are implemented in a FORTRAN code called CORIN. The radial and interlaminar stresses are obtained for any lay-up configuration, being the tension and shear forces, and bending moment the external loads applied. This methodology has been used by CASA in the European Fighter Aircraft (EFA) and in the Airbus A330/340.

In the EFA, it has been used in the design of the spar caps of the boundary C spar of the wing tank. The development tests carried out were of two types: details (bolted angles in T pull and C angles in pull) and boxes (pressure box).

For the Horizontal Tailplane of the Airbus A330/340, this methodology has been used in the skin to spars joint, where the design concept is different to the EFA. While in the EFA, the skin is bolted to the spar angle, in the Airbus the angle is cocured to the skin and bolted to the spar. The tests performed in the Airbus were details and boxes.

The test results correlation with the theoretical analysis have shown very good concordance. Furthermore, some Finite Element Models using NASTRAN were done to confirm the analytical predictions.

Design rules for minimizing the delamination problems in the corners and some manufacturing recommendations, based on these experience, are also presented in this report.

2. INITIAL ANALYTICAL APPROACH (SIMPLE PROCEDURE)

Consider a beam of rectangular cross section bent around an internal radius R , as illustrated in Figure 3, where the thickness t is small compared to the width. The beam is loaded by a bending moment M . Under these conditions, a two-dimensional stress field is assumed.

The differential equations of equilibrium, using polar coordinates, can be expressed as:

$$[1] \quad \begin{cases} \frac{\partial \sigma_r}{\partial r} + \frac{1}{r} \frac{\partial \tau_{r\theta}}{\partial \theta} + \frac{\sigma_r - \sigma_\theta}{r} = 0 \\ \frac{\partial \tau_{r\theta}}{\partial r} + \frac{1}{r} \frac{\partial \sigma_\theta}{\partial \theta} + 2 \frac{\tau_{r\theta}}{r} = 0 \end{cases}$$

These equations are not material dependent and are only valid with neglectable volume forces.

In this case, the beam is composed by an arbitrary number m of plies, each ply having its own thickness and elastic properties (See Figure 4).

Due to the circumferential symmetry of the pure bending:

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial \theta} \tau_{r\theta} = 0; \quad \frac{\partial \sigma_\theta}{\partial \theta} = 0$$

and then

$$[2] \quad \begin{cases} \frac{d}{dr} (r\sigma_r) = \sigma_\theta \\ \frac{d\tau_{r\theta}}{dr} + \frac{2\tau_{r\theta}}{r} = 0 \end{cases}$$

It can be assumed, as a preliminary approach, that the circumferential stress distribution along the cross section $\sigma_\theta(r)$ is similar to the bending stress distribution on a straight composite beam, given in chapter 18 of Reference (1):

$$[3] \quad \sigma^{(l)} = \frac{6E_\theta^{(l)}}{\delta} M [2S_1 y - S_2]$$

where

ℓ = ply identifier

$y = R+t-r$

$$S_1 = \sum_{l=1}^m E_\theta^{(l)} (b_l - b_{l-1})$$

$$S_2 = \sum_{l=1}^m E_\theta^{(l)} (b_l^2 - b_{l-1}^2)$$

$$S_3 = \sum_{l=1}^m E_\theta^{(l)} (b_l^3 - b_{l-1}^3)$$

$$S = 4S_1 S_3 - 3S_2^2$$

$E_\theta^{(l)}$ is the Young's modulus for the ply l in tangential direction.

Using the expression [3], the radial stress distribution $\sigma_r(r)$ can be obtained, by integration, from first equation of [2]:

$$[4] \quad \sigma_r^{(l-1,l)} = -\frac{6M}{S(R+t-b_{l-1})} \sum_{i=1}^{l-1} E_\theta^{(i)} [S_1(b_i^2 - b_{i-1}^2) - S_2(b_i - b_{i-1})]$$

This is preliminary expression of the interlaminar radial stress between the plies $l-1$ and l .

For the case of pure bending is easy to demonstrate from the second equation of [2] and the boundary conditions, that $\tau_{r\theta} = 0$.

3. GENERAL PROBLEM (COMPLEX PROCEDURE)

The general problem of a composite curved beam with bending moment, tension and shear force applied at the end is shown schematically in Figure 5. The beam is assumed clamped in the non externally loaded end.

The way to solve the problem is to define stress functions F matching the differential equation of compatibility inside each ply, and fix the coefficients of F imposing boundary conditions. There are two kind of conditions to impose:

- Global conditions:
 - support
 - loading
- Local conditions:
 - Continuity between plies of stresses and displacements

Using that procedure is possible to establish a system of linear equations that defines the stress functions coefficients, and then, solve the problem.

The stress function of each ply can be written

$$[5] \quad F = f_0 + f_1 \cos\theta + f_2 \sin\theta$$

where:

$$\begin{aligned} f_0 &= A + Br^2 + Cr^{1+K} + Dr^{1-K} \\ f_1 &= A_1 r^{1+\beta} + B_1 r^{1-\beta} + C_1 r + D_1 r \log r \\ f_2 &= A_2 r^{1+\beta} + B_2 r^{1-\beta} + C_2 r + D_2 r \log r \\ K &= \sqrt{\frac{E_\theta}{E_r}} \\ \beta &= \sqrt{1 + \frac{E_\theta}{E_r} (1 - 2\nu_r) + \frac{E_\theta}{E_r}} \end{aligned}$$

E_r , E_θ are the Young's moduli for tension in the radial and tangential directions. These stress functions fulfill the differential equation of compatibility given in chapter 10 of Ref. (1).

The stress components will be expressed by stress function F (for each ply individually):

$$[6] \quad \begin{cases} \sigma_r = \frac{1}{r} \frac{\partial F}{\partial r} + \frac{1}{r^2} \frac{\partial^2 F}{\partial \theta^2} \\ \sigma_\theta = \frac{\partial^2 F}{\partial r^2} \\ \tau_{r\theta} = \frac{1}{r^2} \frac{\partial F}{\partial \theta} - \frac{1}{r} \frac{\partial^2 F}{\partial r \partial \theta} \end{cases}$$

The generalized Hooke's law:

$$\begin{cases} \varepsilon_r = a_{11}\sigma_r + a_{12}\sigma_\theta + a_{16}\tau_{r\theta} \\ \varepsilon_\theta = a_{12}\sigma_r + a_{22}\sigma_\theta + a_{26}\tau_{r\theta} \\ \varepsilon_{r\theta} = a_{16}\sigma_r + a_{26}\sigma_\theta + a_{66}\tau_{r\theta} \end{cases}$$

Each individual ply of the beam can be considered as an orthotropic beam with cylindrical anisotropy. Then the generalized Hooke's law can be written in the form of:

$$[7] \quad \begin{cases} \varepsilon_r = \frac{1}{E_r} \sigma_r - \frac{\nu_\theta}{E_\theta} \sigma_\theta \\ \varepsilon_\theta = -\frac{\nu_r}{E_r} \sigma_r + \frac{1}{E_\theta} \sigma_\theta \\ \tau_{r\theta} = \frac{1}{G_{r\theta}} \tau_{r\theta} \end{cases}$$

Displacement components are determined, by integration, from the equations:

$$[8] \quad \begin{cases} \varepsilon_r = \frac{\partial u_r}{\partial r} \\ \varepsilon_\theta = \frac{1}{r} \frac{\partial u_\theta}{\partial \theta} + \frac{u_r}{r} \\ \gamma_{r\theta} = \frac{1}{r} \frac{\partial u_r}{\partial \theta} + \frac{\partial u_\theta}{\partial r} - \frac{u_\theta}{r} \end{cases}$$

and can be written by the coefficients of the stress function using the equations [6] and [7].

The coefficients of the stress function for each ply are determined solving the system of linear equations given by the imposing of the boundary conditions:

- Continuity ply to ply (no slippage nor separation)

$$\text{at } r = r_{l-1} \quad \begin{matrix} u_r^{(l-1)} = u_r^{(l)}; u_\theta^{(l-1)} = u_\theta^{(l)} \\ \sigma_r^{(l-1)} = \sigma_r^{(l)}; \tau_{r\theta}^{(l-1)} = \tau_{r\theta}^{(l)} \end{matrix}$$

- The boundary conditions at the external and internal radius are:

$$\text{at } r = R \quad \sigma_r^{(m)} = \tau_{r\theta}^{(m)} = 0$$

$$\text{at } r = R + t \quad \sigma_r^{(1)} = \tau_{r\theta}^{(1)} = 0$$

- Loading conditons. The stresses in each cross section should balance the external loading (See Figure 5):

$$\sum_{l=1}^m \int_{r_l}^{r_{l-1}} \tau_{r\theta}^{(l)} dr = F_c \cos\theta - F_t \sin\theta$$

$$\sum_{l=1}^m \int_{r_l}^{r_{l-1}} \sigma_\theta^{(l)} dr = F_c \sin\theta + F_t \cos\theta$$

$$- \sum_{l=1}^m \int_{r_l}^{r_{l-1}} \sigma_\theta^{(l)} (r - \bar{r}) dr = M + F_c \bar{r} \sin\theta - F_t \bar{r} (1 - \cos\theta)$$

where \bar{r} is the radial coordinate of the neutral axis of the beam.

The complete development of these expressions is given in Ref. (3).

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Using the procedures described in this paper, a FORTRAN code program has been produced. The program calculate stresses in each ply along the corner thickness. In order to determine the possible failure due to the delamination, the quadratic delamination criterium proposed in ref. (2) has been used:

$$\left(\frac{\sigma_r}{\sigma_{ra}}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{\tau_{r\theta}}{ILSS}\right)^2 = d^2 \quad \begin{matrix} d < 1 \text{ no failure} \\ d \geq 1 \text{ failure} \end{matrix}$$

Where:

σ_{ra} : Allowable radial tensile stress.

ILSS : Allowable interlaminar shear stress.

Comparisons have been performed to assess te accuracy of the present method. The first problem considered was an isotropic curved bar in bending. Figure 6 shows the results compared with the solution given by the Timoshenko (4) for isotropic

The next problem is a composite curved beam. Comparison have done between the present method and the results given in Ref. (5). The same properties stated in Ref. (5) have been used for the comparison. These properties are given in Table 1.

Figure 7 shows the results for several lay-ups. There is an excellent agreement between the present method and the previous numerical results of ref. (5).

For the EFA and AIRBUS, dedicated test programmes have been performed in order to obtain interlaminar stress allowables in the corner zone.

The results show an allowable mean value for radial stress lower than the ply transverse tensile strength and, due to the variability, the value is going appreciably down when calculating the statistic "B basis" allowable. These effects are probably due to usual manufacturing problems and become dramatic when detectable defects (delaminations, inclusions, etc.), were present in the test specimens. As a result, the ply transverse tensile strength is not an usefull value for allowable tensile radial stress (peeling). In order to illustrate this reduction, a typical example is given in figure 8.

5. DESIGN RECOMENDATIONS

Based on the analysis performed using the methodology described above, and the results of EFA and Airbus test programmes, the following design recommendations can be given:

- Design criteria based on isotropic material tradicional rules should not be used. The composite angles are often critical for a level of radial and transverse shear stresses that would not be critical for isotropic materials.
- In the design of the surrounding structure, the bending moment in the corner should be minimized (stiffeness relation, position of bolts, etc.).
- The angle strength increases for higher internal radio. Figure 9 shows the increasing of the delamination strength with the ratio R/t for all the laminates represented. The parameter γ is the bending moment strength divided by t^2 and σ_{ra} .
- Lay-ups with better "bending efficiency" have a higher angle strength. In figure 9 the parameter:

$$\lambda = \frac{12D_x}{E_x t^3}$$

is an index of the "bending efficiency" of lay-up and the graphics show that this parameter is very important in the strength of the angle.

- Design the angles for male tool, due to the following advantage:
 - a) The manufacturing operation of building up the lay-up is easier.
 - b) A better compactation is achieved (higher σ_{ra}).
 - c) No wrinkles in corners.
 - d) Internal radii are more accurate.
 - e) Posibility of hot-forming and automatic lay-up operation.
- The only disadvantage of the male against female tools is the posibility of thickness reduction (less of the nominal thickness) in the corner area, due to flow of the resin. This reduction has to be controlled and minimized during the manufacturing process.

- The design should be based on interlaminar allowables obtained from dedicated test specimens representing the angle configuration with manufacturing tolerated defects and under environmental conditions.

6. REFERENCES

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Fig. 1

Fig. 2

Fig. 3

Fig. 4

Fig. 5

Table 1. Material properties used in comparison.

Ply longitudinal modulus	$E_{x,x} = 146800 MP_a$
Ply transverse modulus	$F_{y,y} = 11400 MP_a$
In plane shear modulus	$G_{x,y} = 6184 MP_a$
Poisson ratio	$\nu_{x,y} = 0.3$
Ply shear strength	$S = 133.7 MP_a$
Ply transverse tensile strength	$Y_T = 26.8 MP_a$

FIGURE 7

FIG. 8
ALLOWABLE RADIAL STRESS

FIGURE 9.